

DEVELOPING LIBRARY LITERACY COMPETENCE IN PRIMARY STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18065225>

Abstract. *This article analyzes the problem of competence in developing reading literacy in primary school students from a pedagogical point of view, and also provides information about the legal basis. Also, the author's thoughts and opinions on the methods and importance of developing reading literacy in primary school students are presented in a well-founded way, linking them with real-life examples.*

Keywords: *book, competence, literacy, student, teacher, parent, ability, education, upbringing, opportunity.*

INTRODUCTION. Today, reading literacy is of great importance in the education system. Developing students' reading skills, in addition to providing them with knowledge, also forms their thinking skills. Developing reading literacy for primary school students serves as the foundation for their future success. In this regard, on January 12, 2017, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev issued a decree "On increasing book reading and reading culture"[2]. This, in turn, is an important step towards increasing the level of reading in our country and the publication of new, rich books. Using such opportunities wisely and reading new, rich works of literature will allow young people to grow in consciousness, deepen their thinking, and acquire their own independent opinion. It should also be noted that the five initiatives put forward by our president have become an important factor in further supporting young people today. An important program is being implemented: "Organizing systematic work to improve the spirituality of young people and widely promote reading among them"[3].

Reading literacy is the ability of students to read, understand, and use books. This process not only helps students acquire information, but also develops their thinking, analytical, and problem-solving skills. Reading literacy also broadens students' culture and worldview.

METHODS. It is known that reading plays an invaluable role in the education and development of a person. In the primary grades, literary reading lessons work on works of various genres. The first literary works that a young student gets acquainted with are fairy tales. The world of fairy tales for children is beautiful and exciting. They are attracted by the sharp, interesting plot of fairy tales, the unusual setting in which events take place, and the characters. The narration itself, the melodious language, the special syllable of speech, and the composition arouse interest. It is not surprising that the great fairy tale lover A.S. Pushkin noted: "How charming these fairy tales are! Each of them is a poem!" The strength of fairy tales is their active, effective focus on victory, the triumph of truth, their main ending, which is especially interesting for children. Fairy tales serve to restore the spiritual experience of our culture, the traditions of our people. "A fairy tale," wrote V.A. Sukhomlinsky, "develops the child's inner strength, thanks to which a person cannot help but do good, that is, it teaches empathy." Helping a hero in trouble, the desire to

understand the situation in a fairy tale - all this stimulates the child's mental activity, develops interest in the subject, observation, thinking imagination, the ability to remember, emotions and imaginary memory, a sense of humor, forms the ability to master the terminology of evaluation, teaches to see the unusual. The text of fairy tales is an excellent material for the formation of coherent speech skills.

We turned to the topic "Methodology of studying fairy tales in primary grades", because in our time the problem of lack of interest in reading among children of primary school age is the most urgent. It's time to think: why, given the modern organization of teaching reading in primary grades, do our children not read enough, why does their interest in reading decrease, and what needs to be done to eliminate these negative phenomena?

What methods and techniques can be used to restore interest in reading? How to organize the work of a teacher so that inquisitiveness, a light of curiosity for a work of art is kindled in a child's soul, and a passion for turning to books accompanies him throughout his life? As is known, a fairy tale is a widespread and ancient genre of folk oral literature, an epic, prosaic, plot genre. ... It is not sung like a song, but told. The theme of the story in it is unusual, amazing, and often mysterious and strange events. A fairy tale is distinguished from other prosaic genres by its highly developed aesthetic side. The aesthetic principle is manifested in the idealization of positive characters, in the vivid depiction of the "fairy world", in the romantic coloring of events. Some believe that fairy tales are epic, mainly magical, adventurous works of literary prose, and attention is paid to fiction... The principle of the artistic style of a fairy tale determines its ideological content, theme, language, plot character, narrative character, but does not deprive it of its connection with reality. Others believe that the main feature of a fairy tale is not its attitude to fiction, but its attitude to revealing the truth of life with the help of conventionally poetic fiction, which elevates or lowers reality.

Various interpretations and explanations of the concept of "fairy tale" are reflected in all kinds of dictionaries and reference encyclopedias. Let's consider some of them. "Explanatory Dictionary of the Russian Language" S.I. Ozhegov identifies two main meanings of the word "fairy tale": "1. A story about a fictional character and events, mainly involving magical, fantastic forces, usually a folk-poetic work. 2. Fiction, lie, hoax (colloquialism).

In the scientific collection of ethnographic concepts and terms, the definition is most widespread: "Fairy tales are a type of oral folk prose that performs an aesthetic function. This distinguishes them from other oral stories, in which the main function is informative (legends, stories, etc.). (i.e., the orientation towards fiction) essentially remains the only characteristic that allows us to classify oral stories as tales told for the purpose of entertainment and education ... ". "A tale is any oral story told for the purpose of entertaining the audience" - this is the definition given by the literary encyclopedia. The Krugosvet encyclopedia notes that "a tale is one of the types of folklore prose found among different peoples and, in turn, divided into genres."

The poetic dictionary of A.P. Kvyatkovsky contains the following definition: "A fairy tale is the most ancient folk genre of narrative literature, mainly of a fantastic character, aimed at moralizing or entertaining.

RESULTS. Fairy tales reveal the character of the people, their wisdom, and high moral qualities. ." A fairy tale is a wonderful work of art. The word fairy tale as an independent word was first recorded in the "Handwriting Lexicon" in the first half of the 18th century. In the meaning of "fairy tale-fable", and in relation to a literary work, it is first found in the works of A.P. Sumaronova, M.V. Lomonosov. An attempt to separate a fairy tale from other genres of folklore

was put forward more than 100 years ago by K.S. Aksakov. He believed that a fairy tale and a song are different: a fairy tale is a fold (fiction), and a song is a truth. As Aksakov noted, the most characteristic feature of fairy tales is fiction, moreover, a conscious one. He did not recognize the idea that a "empty fold" could remain with the people for several centuries. A.N. Afanasyev believed that a fairy tale is not an ordinary fold, it is caused by reality, some objective realities of people's life. E.V. Pomerantseva One of the main features of a fairy tale its future orientation expressed the idea that fairy tales "overcome reality." Many definitions still cannot fully reveal the essence of a fairy tale and require additional explanation. This is because defining a fairy tale as a genre is problematic due to its versatility. Each of the researchers focuses on one or another aspect of the concept. The most correct and complete, in our opinion, is the definition given by the largest collector and researcher of fairy tales, A.I. Nikiforov: "Fairy tales are oral stories spread among the people for entertainment purposes, containing unusual (fantastic, fabulous or everyday) events in the everyday sense, and characterized by a unique compositional and stylistic construction." Thus, there are three main features inherent in a fairy tale: "a goal-oriented attitude of the audience to entertainment", "unusual content in the everyday sense" and "a special form of construction". The action in a fairy tale has an adventurous character. The plot is distinguished by its multi-episode nature, completeness, dramatic tension, clarity and dynamism in the development of action.

The fairy tale is characterized by a strict form, the obligatory nature of certain moments, as well as a traditional beginning and ending. The beginning takes the listeners from reality to the world of fairy tales, and the end returns them again. He humorously emphasizes that fairy tales are fiction. Fairy tales are rich material for the moral education of children. Studying the plot of the fairy tale, the child, together with the hero, goes through all the stages, gets acquainted with possible life situations, forms the necessary skills to solve and overcome them, "educates" them; The cognitive side of the fairy tale is of great importance. They remain the first and necessary step in knowledge to this day. Through them, the multilayered culture of our contemporaries of past eras, the universal ties of our contemporaries with the cultures of other neighboring and distant peoples are revealed; the fairy tale is used as a means of developing the speech of students. Younger schoolchildren voluntarily tell fairy tales, while retaining the wonderful figurative expressions and descriptive means (comparisons, epithets), as well as the specific syntactic structure of speech, sentence structure, and the liveliness of the story adopted in fairy tales.

DISCUSSION. In recent years, the scale of work on promoting a reading culture among young people in our country has increased to a qualitative level. In particular, the Resolution of the President of Uzbekistan dated September 13, 2017 "On the Program of Comprehensive Measures to Develop the System of Publishing and Distribution of Book Products, Enhance and Promote the Culture of Book Reading and Reading"[4], the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers dated December 14, 2020 No. 781, the National Program for the Development and Support of a Reading Culture in 2020–2025, and a number of other documents serve as a roadmap for the development of the sector.

The development of a system for assessing the effectiveness of measures taken to develop reading, the introduction of ratings such as "The Best Reading Area", "The Best Reading Neighborhood", "The Best Reading Educational Institution", and other important tasks have been set.

Books collect the masterpieces of human thought and pass them on to future generations. In fact, no other source can enhance human maturity like books. Each reader, based on their age

group, has the opportunity to read works of art or scientific works, and to understand the ideas they cover more deeply. For this, the interests of the child should be fully studied in cooperation with parents, kindergartens, and schools. As they say, one child is worth seven parents, everyone is equally responsible for raising a child and ensuring that they grow up spiritually and culturally. It is not for nothing that they say that a family that does not have the habit of reading books is a spiritually poor family. Therefore, not only parents, but also library staff should be highly qualified specialists in their profession and choose the right books for readers, taking into account their interests.

In the pedagogy of children's reading, the growth of reading is divided into the following stages depending on age: childhood 6-9 years; transition from childhood to adolescence 10-11 years; adolescence 12-13 years; transition from adolescence to adolescence is considered 14 years. The age limit of these categories is flexible, that is, depending on the formation of the socio-psychological conditions of the reader, a 10-year-old child can be included in the category of adolescent readers, depending on the specific typological characteristics, and 14-year-olds can be included in the category of readers who are in the transition to adolescence.[6]

The importance of developing reading literacy in primary school students:

1. Reading books increases children's thinking skills.
2. Books develop children's language and speech.
3. Children are given the opportunity to experience different emotions in relation to the works they read, which develops their emotional intelligence.
4. Students get acquainted with different cultures, traditions and moral values through books.

Nowadays, the tradition of reading books has been somewhat lagging behind. Our modern youth is more busy with phone or computer games than reading books. In a modern country, it is good to keep up with the times, but a person cannot find the nourishment he gets from books in anything else.

Today, in many families, there is almost no time for family reading. In most families, the head of the household is always busy with work, so after dinner, they either sit down by the window to write off the day's fatigue, or prefer to sleep to relax. There are even families where the parents themselves prefer to spend time at home with their phones and computers rather than with their children. Instead of putting up with their children's whims, being close to them spiritually, and being interested in their achievements and problems, their studies are left to their teachers or only their mastery of academic subjects is monitored, and education and upbringing are largely the work of teachers and trainers in educational institutions. A child who is left alone or unsupervised for the rest of the day will mostly prepare his own lessons. A child who has not yet fully understood black and white, necessary and unnecessary things, and who is still in his early childhood years, will "make friends" with the blue screen, spending most of his time in front of it, but will go through his days without understanding the essence of the programs he watches or the knowledge he has learned. The saddest thing is that most young people are now becoming ardent fans of various types of mobile communication devices or computer equipment, which have become firmly entrenched in the memory of entertainment games (even more terrible is the abundance of shooting, murder, militancy, and fighting scenes in most of these games), and of films and pictures downloaded from the Internet that are not suitable for their age. Just as a child does not know how to read, does not understand what he reads, or does not understand its essence, he cannot get any knowledge or pleasure from it, so he cannot get any aesthetic pleasure or spiritual

strength from such illicit games. On the contrary, a number of negative vices such as thoughtlessness, frivolity, nervousness, carelessness, indifference, irresponsibility, laziness, and aimlessness are formed in him, which become increasingly firmly entrenched in his psyche and character.

We considered the following as important methods for developing reading competence in primary school students:

1. It is necessary to create a comfortable and attractive reading environment in the classroom. Corners filled with books, comfortable seating areas, and bright colors attract the attention of children.

2. It is important to organize reading programs and projects that interest students. For example, "Book Week" or "About the Book I Read" projects.

3. It is necessary to involve parents in encouraging their children to read books. Parents can read books to their children themselves or read together.

4. Teachers should give children recommendations about books, interest them, and actively participate in the reading process.

5. Offering students books of different genres increases their interest. Genres such as stories, fairy tales, and science fiction expand children's imagination.

Therefore, every parent should pay special attention to the physical, mental, spiritual and spiritual upbringing of their child, provide them with age-appropriate fiction books, exchange ideas with them about the books they read, and encourage the child.

"We need to provide our youth with a decent education, realize their aspirations for science. To this end, we need to develop the preschool education system, radically improve the material and technical base of secondary and tertiary educational institutions, and the quality of scientific and educational processes," says our head of state.[1]

The educational sector cannot be imagined without books. In the educational process, both students and teachers directly feel the need to read books. This is, of course, gratifying. However, nowadays, since students mainly use scientific literature, textbooks and manuals, their opportunities to devote time to reading works of art are limited. The student is only acquiring works of art to complete the task assigned by the teacher in literature class.

As a result, it is clear: the process of reading becomes an obligation, not a hobby. A student who does not develop a passion for reading books from childhood will not find the strength to read the large works given later, will not feel the enthusiasm, will not express the desire, will only get acquainted with the abbreviated excerpts given in the textbook and will not fully understand the pathos, the ideological and artistic purpose that the author has embedded in the entire content of the work, will be deprived of the true pleasure of works of art, will not feel the true power and might of literature, and as a result, will not love reading books.

There are many negative consequences of low reading: a person's ability to think independently, deeply perceive reality, react to events, and distinguish between black and white is not fully formed; he is not widely acquainted with national culture, history, and traditions; he develops spiritual poverty and weakness; when faced with problems in life, he has difficulty finding solutions, considers himself weak; his literacy is low, and due to a lack of vocabulary, he cannot fully express his thoughts; he has difficulty creating compositionally perfect texts and constructing sentences that meet the requirements for cultural speech (such as clarity, correctness, logical coherence, expressiveness, and purity). As proof of this, we can say that when we have students write essays, reports, and dictations in native language and literature classes, we see that

most students' written work contains a lot of spelling, punctuation, and stylistic errors, and that the level of creative work of most students is very low.

Even when analyzing the ideological and artistic aspects of the literary works studied in class and discussing their aesthetic impact, the student cannot express a coherent opinion or react. When we talk to the student, they cannot say when they last read a literary work, and when we ask them to list the literary works they have read, unfortunately, their names are limited. To overcome such problems, we assign students to read one literary work of a certain title every week and, within a specified period, we study the ideological and artistic aspects of that work with the group of students.

When we analyze the works given for independent reading, we see that the student's desire to read fiction books has increased, and he experiences surprise and pleasure. So, in order to satisfy the spiritual needs of the younger generation, it is necessary to regularly teach them how to choose books, read them, and analyze them, and for this, in our opinion, it would be appropriate to increase the number of lessons in literature and the native language, and organize classes in groups. As a result, the possibility of an individual approach to students increases, and the effectiveness of lessons increases. Also, students have more conversations with specialist teachers and learn from their experience. In the process of education, the humanities, psychology, and ethics of literature lessons are fully manifested in the preparation of truly patriotic, capable, and courageous young people, ideologically and intellectually mature personnel, who meet the needs of the times, and in meeting the necessary spiritual needs.

Undoubtedly, the needs of people will continue to increase, but the value of spiritual needs will increase in any era, and will never disappear. Spiritual decline leads to the decline of society, and spiritual perfection serves as the main solid foundation for the development of society.

CONCLUSION. So, fairy tales are an inexhaustible source of moral, labor, patriotic, aesthetic education of students. Fairy tales occupy an important place among other works of folk oral art and are one of the most beloved literary genres by children. Children and fairy tales are inseparable, they are created for each other, therefore, acquaintance with the fairy tales of their people should be included in the education and upbringing course of every child. In conclusion, we can say that a book is one of the closest friends. We find answers to questions through books, books are the most important food for thought. Books invite you to the best intellectual rest and flight of imagination.

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